

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

THE PANDEMIC THAT POSES CHALLENGES BEYOND HEALTH

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POLICY STATEMENT

The more we can advance in knowledge about the New Coronavirus (COVID-19), the greater are the chances of fighting it. In this sense, the achievements of the science have been impressive. However, it is essential to reflect on the impacts of the current pandemic on the economic, political, and social spheres, beyond the acceleration of the reorganization of global power whose epicenter may no longer be restricted to the developed West. Concerning the economy, the scenario is of bankruptcies and market concentration among large companies. In the orbit of politics, polarization and worsening of xenophobic nationalism. In the social sphere, unemployment and increasing inequalities. About global power, the growing projection of East Asia is imposed on decision-makers at the same speed with which dissent divides opinions on these themes.

BACKGROUND

The world was not prepared for the New Coronavirus, and this is not historical news. Because of this reality, which reached a pandemic status, announced in March 2020 by the WHO, social detachment and commercial activities' interruption became the only alternatives to various countries. Initially, such measures seemed sufficient to contain the spread of the virus. Still, pressures favorable to the relaxation of restrictions promoted the easing of actions and, consequently, increased cases. On November 4th, 2020, the world was facing a new record in the number of cases registered per day: 685,000, with more than 1.2 million dead (1). By that time, more than 48 million people were infected. Exactly three months later, the number of infected people reaches more than 83 million confirmed cases, with more than 1.8 million deaths (2). Furthermore, it is crucial to consider that global conditions are becoming more and more conducive to viral spread and that this is not the last or worst pandemic to be faced in this century (3).

Needless to say, that the economic and social effects of the current pandemic could extend for decades. Despite the different approaches presented to date, it's not exaggerated to account for a 5% drop in world production in 2020. By way of illustration, more than one billion children have had their studies interrupted or impaired somehow, and around 200 million people in 2030 will be able to join the ranks of those who already live in extreme poverty (4). In summary, everyone will suffer, directly or indirectly, from the ordeal imposed by the pandemic.

FINDINGS

Unlike military stalemates, such as those that occurred during the Cold War, or terrorist attacks, such as those that occurred on September 11, 2001, the pandemic caused by the New Coronavirus has no apparent culprits or villains, nor triggers to be fought. In addition to the above, and despite the health crisis being a risk to all human beings, not everyone recognizes and processes information in the same way. Seen in this light, the personal experience of losing a relative or friend, by COVID-19, may be more decisive for a change in behavior than a statistical sequence involving the exponential increase in cases or deaths from the disease (5).

As written above, it is worth paying attention to the growing negationist, nationalist and xenophobic stances taken by some countries, as well as to the possible emergence of these or other trends considered threats to human rights, being sure that the upsurge of policies linked to national borders, as a reflection such conducts would have little or no effect, as there is no sufficiently effective border policy against viruses.

The impressive numbers reveal the inadequacy of the global systems in place to protect against pandemics. The current public health architecture was built for outbreaks and epidemics, but pandemics require a different approach. In outbreaks and epidemics, the spread of the disease is geographically limited, so that non-affected countries can, at least in theory, help those affected. However, in a pandemic, almost everyone is involved simultaneously, which means a more significant and simultaneous demand for resources from international organizations. In this case, it does not seem enough that countries trust themselves and each other to prevent the spreading. Strengthened interagency relationships would be invaluable in this context.

The beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic was a massive shock to the global economy. The synchronized shutdown in the first half of 2020 was the most significant, fastest, and most comprehensive reduction in economic activity ever witnessed in the modern world. Measures have been taken, especially by the corporate world, but everything indicates that they are measures with short-term effects. Loans aimed at coping with the collapse of demand may temporarily calm investors. Still, they will not guarantee long-term results, a lesson that should have been learned during the recent financial crisis, which started in 2008. (6)

CONCLUSIONS

As imagined, the impact on supply and demand was most felt by less favored families, whose members were more likely to lose their jobs and had little financial breath to cross the period. This may be a propitious moment for state protagonism and unification of public and private agendas. Opportunities and lives lost, political careers destroyed, increased extreme poverty, ideological polarization, geopolitical disaster, and the certainty that isolated actions are not only unpopular but ineffective. There is no room for opportunism when the enemy is a pandemic. Disputes that are divided into a winner on the one hand and a loser on the other, whether that winner is a power, a government, an interest group, a person, or an idea, simply because it is a unit in itself, no longer fits in the world that we create.

SUGGESTIONS

To deal with the consequences of the current pandemic caused by the new Coronavirus, with its variants and the risks of new pandemics, considering the critical literature available and the impacts that go beyond the health sphere, the following points must be considered:

- Inter-agency relationships must be strengthened and have clear and well-targeted agendas.
- The recognition of the benefits of public-private partnerships.
- Research and training structured based on collective interests should be guided by human rights.
- The organization of a detailed database containing good practices and misconceptions related to preventing and facing public health challenges.
- Repositioning of economic issues and non-collective interests concerning the public health imperative.
- The observation and/or reformulation of the International Health Regulations (IHR), taking advantage of the effort made so far and the advances in the field of public health (7).

Challenges to be faced and mitigated:

- Disputes in between agencies for greater visibility.
- Conflicts between public and private spheres.
- Synergy regarding global collective interests.

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